

Blockade of cAMP/PKA-signaling

in mesenchymal progenitor cells as a promising approach to wound healing

Bloqueo de la señalización cAMP/PKA en células progenitoras mesenquimales como un enfoque prometedor para la cicatrización de heridas

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Abstract

The wound healing properties of the cAMP/PKA-signaling blocker was investigated. On the model of the skin wound the pronounced wound healing effects of the PKA inhibitor have been revealed. Implementation of the identified effects was associated with activation of mesenchymal progenitors (MPC) functions in granulation tissue. The development of this phenomenon is associated with direct exposure of the pharmacological agent to MPC in the conditions of their influence of growth factors (in particular, the growth factor of fibroblasts (FGF) secreted by stromal cells in situ. In this case, there is an increase not only in the proliferation of activity but also in the intensity of the specialization processes of progenitors. In a medium without cytokines, the cAMP/PKA-signaling blocker causes the progression of the cell signal but does not affect the rate of maturation of precursors.

Keywords: cAMP/PKA-signaling, progenitors, skin wound, targeted therapy, regenerative medicine.

Resumen

Se investigaron las propiedades curativas de la herida del bloqueador de señalización de cAMP/PKA. En el modelo de la herida de la piel se han revelado los efectos pronunciados de curación de heridas del inhibidor de la PKA. La implementación de los efectos identificados se asoció con la activación de funciones progenitoras mesenquimales (MPC) en el tejido de granulación. El desarrollo de este fenómeno se asocia con la exposición directa del agente farmacológico a MPC en las condiciones de su influencia de los factores de crecimiento (en particular, el factor de crecimiento de los fibroblastos (FCF) secretados por células estromales in situ. En este caso, hay un aumento no sólo en la proliferación de la actividad, sino también en la intensidad de los procesos de especialización de los progenitores. En medio sin citoquinas, el bloqueador de señalización de cAMP/PKA provoca la progresión de la señal celular, pero no afecta a la tasa de maduración de precusores.

Palabras clave: señalización de cAMP/PKA, progenitores, herida cutánea, terapia dirigida, medicina regenerativa.

Introduction

A promising approach to solving the problems of regenerative medicine is a new direction of pharmacotherapy - "Strategy of targeted pharmacological regulation of intracellular signal transduction in regeneration-competent cells"¹⁻⁴.

It is assumed that the selectivity of stimulation of regeneration of the organs and tissues in need of this will be determined

by the specific role of certain signaling molecules⁶⁻⁷ in the realization of the growth potential of progenitors against the background of tissue specificity of their different types and isoforms (including alternative splicing products)^{1,5,8}.

It is known that one of the key roles in the regulation of proliferation and differentiation of the progenitor cells, as well